

The Dynamics between a CEO and Risk Disclosure in Nigeria

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Abstract

Objective: This paper examines the effects of CEO attributes on risk disclosure by 112 listed firms in Nigeria over a period of 10 years (2012-2021).

Methods: The CEO attributes used include nationality, ownership, gender, turnover, and tenure; while risk disclosure is measured by a dummy variable, which is 1 if disclosed or else 0. The Multiple Regression Analysis is employed in estimating the impacts, over the 10-year period.

Results: The estimation results reveal that the effects of CEO nationality and ownership are positive and significant. The results further reveal that CEO gender, turnover, tenure and ownership are able to significantly respond to risk disclosure. Generally, the estimation results conform to theoretical expectations. The results of the hypotheses tests indicated a significant relationship between the CEO and risk disclosure in Nigeria.

Practical Implications: One major implication of the findings is that listed firms in Nigeria have their CEO playing major role in risk disclosure. It is therefore important for these firms to develop stronger relations between their CEOs and risk disclosure. The paper was motivated by the fact that less attention has been given to the role of CEOs in enhancing risk disclosure among listed firms in Nigeria. Previous research have tended to focus more on deposit money banks. Furthermore, adequate research has yet to be done on how the CEO could enhance risk disclosure among other sectors of the Nigerian economy.

Conclusion: The paper concludes that more research is needed to further assess the impact of various governance mechanisms on corporate risk management and disclosure behaviour. The study is limited by the number of samples, specifically the 112 listed firms in Nigeria. It is expected that further research can increase the total sample of companies or by adding to the research period or using company samples from other Exchanges, not only the Nigerian Exchange. Our study results show that the R-square value in the model is 63%; further research is expected to be able to add other characteristic variables that may influence the role of CEO in enhancing risk disclosure by a company.

Keywords: CEO, gender, nationality, tenure, turnover, ownership, risk disclosure.

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1. Introduction

Risk in business is the likelihood that the objective of the business would not be achieved fully or completely. Therefore, it is both legal and ethical to disclose it, particularly for the benefit of users of accounting information, such as shareholders, creditors, researchers, students, policy-makers and regulators. However, it is easier said than done. A number of listed firms in Nigeria do not disclose the risks that they face in their day to day operations. This must have been the reason why a number of firms in Nigeria failed, despite their promising future. This scenario applies to non-banking sectors in particular, since deposit money banks and other financial services companies such insurance firms, registers, mortgage institutions face strict regulatory controls, from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC) in addition to measures by the Nigerian Securities and Exchange Commission (NSEC) and the Nigerian Exchange (NGX). Out of the 156 listed firms in Nigeria, 44 are classified by the NGX as being in 'red'. The motivation of this paper, therefore is to examine the role of the CEO in minimizing the variability or instability in risk disclosure gravity by listed firms in Nigeria.

The place of a CEO is analytically significant to an organization (Stojanovic-Aleksic, 2016). It is imperative to promote studies on it as the CEO is answerable for the general success of a business organization and for making top-level decisions (Aivazian et al., 2013; Goodall, 2012). Furthermore, the CEO has the final authority in making decisions (Buyl et al., 2011). This leaves a large effect on business financial performance. Previous research on the role of CEO, there are several studies focusing on dissimilar areas. This paper explores the role of the CEO in enhancing risk disclosure among listed firms in Nigeria over a period of 10 years (2012-2021). In order to achieve this objective, the role of the CEO is seen in this paper from five (5) characteristics: gender, nationality, tenure, turnover, and ownership.

CEO gender simply refers to a woman CEO. Women are known to be highly frugal and discipline. When it comes to disclosing risk, women are in prime position. It is important, therefore, to examine the role of women CEOs in risk disclosure in Nigeria. Furthermore, CEO nationality has attracted empirical examination by researchers in recent years. Foreign CEOs are known to embrace hugely, outsourcing as a means of reducing risk they face in their businesses. Therefore, they are largely prone not to disclose all the risks faced by their businesses. Also, CEO tenure may be associated with risk disclosure. A CEO who have spent at least three (3) years in a company is most likely to disclose less of the risks faced by the company due to reason not far from the saying that 'familiarity breeds contempt'. In the same vein, CEO turnover may be associated with the quality of risk disclosure by a company. If CEO is changed in a particular financial year, it is less likely that the new CEO would have a full grip of the company to have full risk disclosure. Furthermore, CEO ownership in a firm may encourage the CEO not to disclose the full length of risks faced by the company due to insider information and agency conflict. CEOs are insiders and agency theory suggests that there may be conflict of interest with the shareholders' interest they are supposed to represent.

The use of listed firms in this paper lends credibility, accountability and transparency to the study. Listed firms are known to face greater and stringent measures from regulatory bodies. The paper is divided into five (5) sections. The remaining four (4) sections cover literature review, methodology, results and discussion, and conclusion and recommendations. This paper is useful to regulators, policy-makers, shareholders, creditors, researchers, and several other stakeholders who may have interest in the nexus between a company's chief executive officer and its risk disclosure quality in Nigeria. The objective of this paper, therefore, is to study the role of chief executive officers, and identify its impact on risk disclosure by listed firms in Nigeria. In this paper, we have focused on the role of Chief Executive Officers from the points of view as CEO gender, nationality, tenure, turnover and share ownership.

2. Literature Review

We have chosen the agency theory as the most appropriate theory for explanation of the nexus between the CEO and risk disclosure in Nigeria. Agency theory suggests that the CEO being a member of the board of directors has privileged information, which may be useable at the detriment of the shareholders. There are quite a number of reported cases of insider dealings by CEOs in Nigeria and World over. Thus, agency theory is used in this paper to help to resolve the conflict of interest between the shareholders and the CEO as far as risk disclosure is concern in Nigeria.

Empirically, Lajili (2009) suggests corporate governance as a solution to corporate risk disclosure by examining the relationships between corporate governance mechanisms and risk disclosure behaviour using a sample of Canadian publicly-traded companies (TSX 230). Results show that Canadian public companies are more likely to disclose risk management information over and above the mandatory risk disclosures, if their CEOs are women and have shares in their companies. Also, Hermalin and Weisbach (2012) show that larger firms will adopt stricter disclosure rules than smaller firms and firms with better disclosure will employ more able management. They further show that mandated increases in disclosure could, in part, explain recent increases in both CEO compensation and CEO turnover rates.

Ali and Taylor (2014) provide evidence on the effects of the background influences of the Chief Executive Officer (CEO) and Chair of Audit Committee (CAC) on corporate risk disclosure of 200 top listed companies in Malaysia. Data was hand-collected from annual reports. The findings in this paper indicate that the CEOs' tenure and ethnicity significantly influence their decision making in regards to corporate risk disclosure. That is, CEOs with ethnicity and with shorter-tenured backgrounds are associated with higher corporate risk disclosure.

Moumen et al. (2016) examine whether board characteristics affect firms' decision to voluntarily disclose informative information about their risk profiles. They base their study on data from 320 listed firms in nine MENA emerging markets (789 observations) over the period from 2007 to 2009. The study offers significant contributions to the growing risk disclosure literature. It provides new empirical evidence that information driven by some board characteristics affects the perceived relevance of narrative risk information. Their findings suggest that the composition of the board and its size enhance the informativeness of risk disclosure as it allows investors to better predict future earnings growth. A further finding is that a CEO/Chairperson duality does not impact the way investors trust risk disclosures.

Carmona et al. (2016) explore the necessary and sufficient conditions of good Corporate Governance practices for high risk disclosure by firms in their Corporate Governance Annual Report. Additionally, they explore whether those recipes have changed during the financial crisis. With a sample of 271 Spanish listed companies, they applied fuzzy-set qualitative comparative analysis to a database of financial and non-financial data. They report that Board of Directors independence, size, level of activity and gender diversity, CEO duality, Audit Committee independence, being audited by the Big Four auditing firms and the presence of institutional investors are associated with high risk disclosure.

Neifar and Jarboui (2018) explore the impact of the mechanisms of corporate governance on the informational content of Operational Risk (OR) voluntary disclosure. The content analysis method was used to collect data on the OR disclosure from annual reports of 34 Islamic banks scattered in various countries and over a period ranging from 2008 to 2014. Using correlation and multiple regression analyses, their results show that the information disclosed on OR, especially that of quality, is considered as value-relevant for investors as they have additional information content in risk assessment of banks. Also, empirical results reveal the significant impact of independent directors on the OR voluntary disclosure reported information. Conversely, the concentration of the chairman and chief executive officer responsibilities on the same person reduces it.

Ibrahim et al. (2018) investigate the influence of corporate governance on risk disclosure level in Saudi Arabia. They examine 408 annual reports of Saudi non-financial-listed firms during 2012-2015. The results show that CEO-Chairperson separation, audit committee effectiveness, state ownership, firm complexity, size and profitability positively affect risk disclosure, while they find no significant correlations for board independence, institutional ownership, auditor type, leverage, and firm age.

Salem et al. (2019) investigate the potential influence of corporate governance mechanisms on risk disclosure quality in Tunisia. The authors examine 152 annual reports of Tunisian non-financial-listed firms during 2008–2013, and use the manual content analysis method to measure the risk disclosure quality. The authors find that the quality of risk disclosure in Tunisian companies is relatively low, and also find that the quality of risk disclosure is positively associated with institutional ownership, board independence, the presence of women on the board, the presence of family members on the board and the independence of audit committee. Managerial ownership has a negative effect on risk disclosure quality.

Al-Shirah et al. (2020) examine the level of risk of disclosure practices and the effect of board of directors' characteristics in the Jordanian context. The sample of this study contains the non-financial Jordanian firms listed on Amman Stock Exchange (ASE). 376 annual reports of the sampled firms over four years from 2014 to 2017 were used. The content analysis approach was used to collect data and to determine the level of risk disclosure by computing the number of risk-related sentences in the annual reporting. To test the study's hypothesis, the random effect model was employed. The results indicate that the board expertise is positively related with the level of risk disclosure. Conversely, CEO duality has a negative impact on the risk disclosure practices.

Ivashkovskaya and Adamu (2021) examine the influence of corporate governance attributes on the corporate risk disclosure in the emerging countries. Board size, non-executive directors, independent directors, board diversity and CEO-duality were the important board of director's composition that was considered as corporate governance variables for this study. The study focuses on South Africa and Nigeria as these countries are among major players in the African emerging market. The sample comprises 42 financial and non-financial firms listed in Nigerian Stock Exchange and Johannesburg Stock Exchange. The data was drawn from 192 annual reports for the year 2014-2018. The analytical tools employed are manual content analysis and regression. The empirical results show that operational risk disclosure outweighs environmental and strategic risk disclosure. Moreover, in considering the important factors that impact on the risk confession, that board size, independent director and diversity have greater influence in driving the risk disclosure upward. Nevertheless, non-executive director and CEO-Duality are statistically insignificant in determining the movement of risk information to divulge.

Sagar et al. (2021) investigate the relationship between gender diversity on board and corporate risk disclosure. Four measures of gender diversity, i.e. BLAU index, SHANNON index, proportion of women directors on board and female dummies, have been deployed to measure gender diversity. The empirical analysis is premised on a sample of S&P BSE 100 index pertaining to the 2018–2019 financial year; which eventually gets reduced to 70 non-financial firms after eliminating 30 financial firms. To examine the impact of gender diversity on corporate risk disclosure, hierarchical regression has been used. Additionally, two-stage least square regression analysis has been performed for checking the endogeneity issues in data and validating the findings of the study. The main findings unveil that gender diversity positively impacts corporate risk disclosure.

Adamu (2021) analyses corporate risk disclosure practice involving listed companies and investigates whether such diverse results are attributable to regulation, jurisdiction, operating industry, business environment, or the methodologies employed. The use risk disclosure, corporate governance and organisational characteristics keywords to search the relevant studies on which 46 empirical research papers were sampled, and employ a meta-analysis procedure to evaluate the findings of the previous empirical research. The analyses reveal that firm size is the major organisational-specific characteristic affected by moderators, and board size and institutional investors are the major corporate governance variables that affect moderators.

Also, Sulistyawati and Suryani (2022) investigate the effect of risk disclosure on the operational efficiency of 130 manufacturing firms listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange in 2019. Risk disclosure was evaluated through the content analysis, while operational efficiency was measured using the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) technique. The data was analysed by utilising weighted least square regression. Results show that risk disclosure positively affects operational efficiency.

Gull et al. (2022) examine the impact of corporate governance reforms on the risk disclosure quality in an emerging economy, namely Pakistan. The authors also investigate the impact of CG reforms on the relationship between CG practices and risk disclosure quality. The authors use a manual content analysis method to a sample of non-financial companies listed on the PSX-100 index for 2009–2015, to examine the impact of CG reforms on risk disclosure quality. The authors use pooled ordinary least squares and the system GMM estimations to test the research hypotheses. The authors find that CG reforms have a positive impact on risk disclosure quality. The results indicate that certain CG practices such as CEO duality and board independence are associated with risk disclosure quality.

On the balance of the findings of these empirical studies, it is convenient to conclude that there are if any few empirical efforts to relate CEO characteristics with risk disclosure. This situation is the motivation of this study, which examines the role of CEO in risk disclosure. By extension, the following five (5) hypotheses are formulated and tested in this paper, that:

- H₁: CEO gender diversity does not significantly affect risk disclosure of listed firms in Nigeria.
- H₂: CEO nationality does not significantly influence risk disclosure of listed firms in Nigeria.
- H₃: CEO tenure does not significantly influence risk disclosure of listed firms in Nigeria.
- H₄: CEO turnover does not significantly influence risk disclosure of listed firms in Nigeria.
- H₅: CEO ownership does not significantly influence risk disclosure of listed firms in Nigeria.

3. Methodology

The research design used in this paper is correlational research design. Correlational research design establishes nexus between or among variables. The population is 156, out of which, 44 were excluded due to questions related to compliance with corporate governance rules as established by the Nigerian Exchange, thus, 112 listed firms form the sample. The model of the study is as follows:

$$RD_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 CEOG_{i,t} + \beta_2 CEON_{i,t} + \beta_3 CEOT_{i,t} + \beta_4 CEOTR_{i,t} + \beta_5 CEOO_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas:

RD = Risk disclosure, measured as dummy where "1" is assigned for companies that have their risks disclosed and "0" for otherwise.

CEOG = CEO Gender, measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that have Female CEOs and "0" for otherwise.

CEON = CEO Nationality, measured as dummy where "1" is assigned for companies that have foreign CEOs and "0" for otherwise.

CEOT = CEO Tenure, measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that have CEOs that have stay for 3 years and "0" for CEOs with less than 3 years tenure.

CEOTR= CEO Turnover, measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that have a change of CEOs in a particular year and "0" for otherwise.

CEOO = CEO Ownership, measured as number of CEO shares divided by total numbers of shares (%).

α = Constant

β_{1-5} = Beta

ε = Error term (Residual)

i = Firm script (firms are 112)

t = Time script (10 years)

CEO data were extracted from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled listed firms from the database of the Nigerian Exchange website. Risk disclosure data was extracted using content analysis. Furthermore, diagnostic tests, such as normality of residuals, heteroskedasticity of residuals, multicollinearity among the CEO attributes, and panel effects were conducted in order to ensure that the model of the study is best linear unbiased estimator (BLUE).

4. Results and Discussion

The descriptive statistics of the study are reported in Table 1. Descriptive statistics are summaries of the data that are used in the study showing the number of observations, central mean, standard deviation, minimum mean, maximum mean, and range.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
RD	1,120	.456	.5	0	1
CEON	1,120	.263	.441	0	1
CEOG	1,120	.019	.136	0	1
CEOT	1,120	.681	.467	0	1
CEOTR	1,120	.194	.396	0	1
CEOO	1,120	2.551	6.772	0	25.081

STATA 16 Outputs

Following from the results in Table 1, the number of observations is 1,120 as earlier indicated under methodology, obtained by the product of the number of firms and the number of years. The mean value of RD is .456 with a standard deviation of .5 and minimum and maximum values of 0 and 1. From these figures, a comparison between the mean and the standard deviation confirm that RD is highly volatile and unstable, which calls for investigation. Also, a minimum mean of 0 means that some of the firms in our sample failed to disclosure their risk disclosure throughout the 10 year-period of this study. In addition, the maximum mean of 1 means that some of the firms in our sample disclosed their risk disclosure.

Furthermore, the mean value of CEON is .263 with a standard deviation of .441 and minimum and maximum values of 0 and 1. That is, the standard deviation is larger than the mean suggesting that some of the firms do not have a foreign CEO. Also, 0 and 1 minimum and maximum means imply that some of the firms have foreign CEO, while some other firms do not have. Additionally, the mean value of CEOG is .019 with a standard deviation of .136 and minimum and maximum values of 0 and 1. Again these figures show a high level of volatility and exposure in the variable. It suggests that most of the CEOs are men. Also, the mean value of CEOT is .681 with a standard deviation of .467 and minimum and maximum values of 0 and 1. In addition, the mean value of CEOTR is .194 with a standard deviation of .396 and minimum and maximum values of 0 and 1. Finally, the mean value of CEOO is 2.551 percent with a standard deviation of 6.772 percent and minimum and maximum values of 0 and 25.081 percent.

Furthermore, we carry out a number of diagnostic tests including normality of residuals, heteroskedasticity of residuals, model specification errors, multicollinearity and panel effects. The results of these tests are reported in Table 2.

Table 2

Results of post estimation tests

Serial	Test	Value
1	Normality of Residuals	.052
2	Homoscedasticity of Residuals	.061
3	Model Specification Error (ovtest)	.135
4	Multicollinearity (mean VIF)	1.32
5	Panel Effects	.127

STATA 16 Outputs

Following from the result of serial 1, in Table 2, it indicates that the residuals are normally distributed since the p-value of normality of residuals test is .052, which is slightly larger than .05 level of significance. The result in serial 2 indicates that there is no presence of homoscedasticity in the model and therefore, there is no need to robust the regression model. The result in serial 3 indicates that there is no model specification error test, that is, the model is well specified. Similarly, the result in serial 4 shows that there is no multicollinearity among the independent. Finally, the panel effects test result shows that there is no panel effects in the model. Thus, the OLS regression model is the appropriate technique to use in this study.

Table 3 presents the results of an OLS regression analysis, since the model shows that there are no panel effects.

Table 3

Results of OLS regression

RD	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
CEON	.14	.092	2.52	.013	.323	.042	*
CEOG	.153	.305	3.50	.006	.448	.755	**
CEOT	.081	.113	2.72	.047	.304	.141	*
CEOTR	.017	.134	2.12	.009	.281	.248	***
CEO	.008	.006	2.22	.022	.005	.02	**
Constant	.53	.106	4.99	.000	.32	.739	***
R-squared		0.630	Number of obs			1120	
F-test		121.13	Prob > F			0.034	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		237.254	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			255.705	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

STATA 16 Outputs

Following from the results in Table 3, the effect of CEON on RD is significant. Therefore, hypothesis one is hereby rejected. In the same vein, the effect of CEOG on RD is significant. Therefore hypothesis two is rejected. Similarly, CEOT shows significance with RD; also, CEOTR shows significance with RD. Finally, CEO shows significance with RD.

On CEO female gender diversity (CEOG), this result is in line with the results of scholars (Benkraiem et al., 2017; Brodmann et al., 2022; Garcia-Blandon et al., 2022; Guli et al., 2018; Khan et al., 2021; Liu, 2018; Ongsakul et al., 2021; Papangkorn, 2021; Simionescu et al., 2021; Solimene et al., 2017; Ullah et al., 2020; Usman et al., 2018; Yahaya, 2022; Zhu et al., 2022). On CEO Nationality, this result is in line with the works of researchers (Billett & Qian, 2018; Madsen & Servais, 1997; Sullivan & Weerawardena, 2006; Zhang & Rajagopalan, 2010).

On CEOT, this result is in line with the results of several scholars (Fajaria & Isnalita, 2018; Farooq & Masood, 2016; Jihadi et al., 2021; Samasta et al., 2018; Verwijmeren & Derwall, 2010). On CEOTR, this result is in line with the works of several scholars (Arias-Aranda et al., 2001; Embong et al., 2012; Muslih & Marbun, 2020; Olawale et al., 2017; Yahaya, 2006; Yahaya & Tijjani, 2021). Finally, on CEOO, the result is in line with the works of scholars (Arias-Aranda et al., 2001; Embong et al., 2012; Muslih & Marbun, 2020; Olawale et al., 2017; Yahaya, 2006; Yahaya & Tijjani, 2021).

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

As can be seen through the empirical results in Tables 1 to 3, it is reasonable to summarize that the overall objective of this study has been achieved, that is, the role of CEO in risk disclosure in Nigeria has been examined. Perhaps, in terms of the specifics, this paper finds CEO nationality, gender, tenure, turnover and share ownership as serving as determinants of risk disclosure among listed firms in Nigeria. Based on these facts, it is recommended that firms' regulators, shareholders, creditors and boards of directors should consider CEOs that share the following characteristics; women, foreign nationality, short tenure, low turnover, and have shares in the companies they manage. This study points to a promising direction for future research to gain a deeper understanding of how the characteristics of the CEO affect risk disclosure decisions of listed firms in Nigeria and regulators, shareholders and boards of directors should consider these characteristics of CEO in appointing CEOs. Furthermore, note that the study is limited by the number of samples, specifically 112 listed companies. It is expected that further research can increase the total sample of companies and also by adding to the research period or using company samples from other exchanges.

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